

Autonomous Price-aware Energy Management System in Smart Homes via Actor-Critic Learning with Predictive Capabilities

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Abstract—The energy consumed by buildings is expected to significantly rise in the upcoming years, necessitating intelligent Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) that create comfortable conditions for their inhabitants, while also offering sustainable and cost-effective solutions. The building environment, however, includes multiple time-varying parameters that cannot be controlled, such as the output of renewable energy sources, the market-dependent electricity prices, the outdoor temperature, as well as the occupants' energy habits. To overcome these barriers, we propose a hybrid Machine Learning (ML) algorithm for smart HEMS control, leveraging the properties of a decision-making deep deterministic policy gradient model, enhanced by the predictive capabilities of long short-term memory networks. Hence, the proposed algorithm aims to achieve an optimal balance between energy cost and occupant comfort by continuously adjusting the energy provided to the heating, ventilation, and air conditioning system, as well as controlling the energy storage system of the smart home. The proposed hybrid method is validated with simulations using real-world data and compared against baseline approaches, showcasing its effectiveness to achieve an optimal trade-off between the indoor temperature deviation and the average energy cost.

Note for practitioners—This paper is motivated by the need of automated energy management in smart buildings to achieve minimal energy consumption. Continuous demands for heating, ventilation and air conditioning, as well as utilization of household loads lead to a significant increase in the daily energy consumption. This paper explores the trade-off between the price that a household pays in return for indoor temperature comfort and coverage of the energy requirements. For this purpose, we provide a comprehensive mathematical modeling of a smart home environment, followed by the description of a real-time decision-making energy management algorithm that is based on Machine Learning (ML). This algorithm takes into account the forecasting of energy consumption and energy production of the household in the future, optimally adjusting the power that is drawn from the grid. By implementing this algorithm using real-world data, we demonstrate that a smart home can maintain a

comfortable indoor temperature, while minimizing the energy cost and boosting the use of local renewable energy. In this context, manufacturers, developers of smart home systems or energy providers that specialize in building automation systems can utilize this algorithm to offer consumers automated energy management that optimizes cost and comfort, leading to sustainable operations. We plan to extend this model to energy communities consisting of multiple smart homes that can also exchange energy surplus to achieve zero-sum energy footprint.

Index Terms—Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL); Energy Demands; Energy Management System; Energy Storage Systems (ESSs); Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) Networks; Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) Systems; Home Automation; Smart Homes.

I. INTRODUCTION

WORLDWIDE, buildings are major energy consumers and one of the most significant contributors to carbon emissions, accounting for about 30% of the world's energy use, while this percentage share is projected to considerably increase in the upcoming years [1]–[3]. In this context, the concept of smart buildings with focused energy management systems has gained increasing prominence, targeting to create sustainable and comfortable environments for their inhabitants, while providing also cost-effective solutions. This trade-off can be accomplished through the integration of cutting-edge technologies including, among others, Internet of Things (IoT), intelligent control and home automation systems that leverage Machine Learning (ML) methods and edge computing [4]–[7]. To this end, the development of innovative smart building energy management strategies, designed to intelligently coordinate the system towards achieving an optimal balance between energy consumption, carbon emissions, operational costs, and occupant comfort is the primary objective of ongoing and future research work [8], [9].

The smart building environment, however, is an extremely dynamic environment that is influenced by several parameters that, in principle, cannot be controlled or even statistically described. To this end, a precise and efficient building thermal dynamics model that represents the internal temperature variations is often unfeasible due to the presence of various complex and unpredictable variables [10], [11]. The management and decision-making system that targets the real-time optimization of the energy consumption is subjected to numerous uncertain parameters such as the output of renewable energy sources (for instance solar panels or wind generators), fluctuating, market-dependent electricity prices, varying environmental ambient

Manuscript received Month Day, Year; revised Month Day, Year and Month Day, Year; accepted Month Day, Year. Date of publication Month Day, Year; date of current version Month Day, Year. This work was partly supported by the “Trustworthy And Resilient Decentralised Intelligence For Edge Systems (TaRDIS)” Project, funded by EU HORIZON EUROPE program, under grant agreement No 101093006. The Associate Editor for this article was Name Surname. (Corresponding author: Sotirios Spantideas.)

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Digital Object Identifier XX.YYYY/TITS.ZZZZ.LLLLLL

temperature, energy-related occupants' habits, etc. [12]. In addition, there may be intricate operational constraints and concealed inter-dependencies amongst the decision variables of the management system, as well as across different energy subsystems. For instance, the Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system is inherently related to the energy storage system (ESSs), as well as the non-controllable and inelastic energy demands of the smart building [13], [14]. Finally, the temporal dimension of the problem under investigation is often disregarded; in principle, decisions made presently influence significantly the future state of the smart building environment and essentially the future choices of the management system, necessitating coordinated decision-making across subsystems [15], [16].

The decision-making system of the building must be therefore able to overcome these challenges, leveraging the dynamic electricity pricing towards reduced energy expenses by smartly managing the ESS and the thermostatically controllable loads. The most significant contributor to the controllable loads is considered the HVAC system, accounting for approximately 40% of a household's total energy consumption and posing a significant concern for the energy expenses of smart homeowners [1]. Considering that the primary role of the HVAC system is to ensure the thermal comfort of residents, keeping the temperature range between desirable limits, it is crucial to balance the optimization of energy costs in smart homes with the maintenance of a comfortable living environment.

A. Related Work

The challenge of enabling a smart home management system to make real-time decisions, aiming to reduce energy costs while maintaining internal thermal comfort, has been explored in various contexts, including model-based and model-free methods. Regarding model-based methods for optimization of the energy consumption for tasks in the smart home and renewable resource efficient management, conventional approaches based on mixed-integer linear programming paradigm have been described [17]. The authors propose an algorithm that ensures optimal task scheduling under dynamic electrical constraints, while maintaining thermal comfort for the residents. For this purpose, a suitable thermal model based on heat-pump usage is developed, while also taking into account the energy-related cost savings due to beneficial task scheduling. Moreover, the authors in [18] develop a multi-objective mixed-integer nonlinear programming model to optimize energy use in a smart home, balancing energy savings with a comfort utility. In this context, they formulate an objective function for joint task scheduling and operation management of various household devices, taking into consideration the energy supply and the user satisfaction levels, while also introducing the different heat generation sources and various heat flows in the thermal modeling of the house. A power scheduling method for demand response in a Home Energy Management System (HEMS) is proposed in [19]. The authors present the HEMS architecture and the available information (real-time demands and electricity price, etc.) that provides the decision-making capabilities of the optimal scheduling scheme for the home

power usage of each electric appliance in the most cost-effective manner. In addition, they base their analysis in a combined real-time pricing and inclining block rate model, utilizing a heuristic algorithm to tackle the non-linearity of the optimization problem of the power scheduling method that reduces the electricity costs and minimizes potentially harmful appliance operation for the the entire electricity system. Furthermore, a HEMS that considers several types of loads with diverse profiles including photovoltaic generation, energy storage, and static demand is proposed in [20]. The developed HEMS targets to optimize the use of local renewable energy, while minimizing energy waste during AC/DC conversions and ESS charging/discharging. To this end, the authors investigate the impact of several modeling parameters in the HEMS control strategy, including the ESS capacity, the AC/DC conversion efficiencies, and the output of the renewable sources, as well as identifying the impact of the load profiles to the household energy cost. Finally, a decoupled demand response strategy and an interdisciplinary mechanism that combines ML, mathematical optimization, and data structure design is proposed in [21]. To this end, the authors present a ML-assisted learning algorithm that understands the energy consumption patterns of the HVAC system, integrating its capabilities with optimization techniques to create optimal demand response policies in real-life environment concerning the varying weather, seasons, and house conditions.

The model-free methods target to design a system that learns optimal behaviors from the data (data-driven model) and by receiving feedback from its actions within the smart home environment. To this end, deep reinforcement learning (DRL) is widely considered a versatile AI technology, exhibiting great potential in tackling the challenges in the modeling process of the complex smart home environment [22]. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in designing HEMS that include DRL-assisted models. For instance, [23] introduces a DRL-based heating controller designed to enhance thermal comfort and reduce energy costs in smart buildings, using real-world outdoor temperature data. The authors present the DRL algorithm that is implemented with a Deep Q-network (DQN) for discrete control actions on the HVAC system. In a similar fashion, the authors in [24] propose OCTOPUS, a system that utilizes a DRL-assisted model, targeting to optimize control sequences for all building subsystems, including HVAC, lighting, blinds, and windows. The DRL model is based on a branching dueling Q-network, effectively addressing the complex control problem arising from the interactions among these four building subsystems. Moreover, the authors in [25] formulate the mathematical framework for a demand response HEMS through price-setting DRL, comparing the performance of a DQN model with a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) network that can be used for continuous actions on the HVAC control.

Regarding hybrid approaches, the authors in [26] introduce DeepComfort, a framework based on DRL for managing the thermal comfort in buildings, formulating a cost-minimization problem and taking into account both the energy consumption of the HVAC system and the thermal comfort of the occupants. The framework utilizes a neural network to predict the

occupants' thermal comfort and a DDPGs method to learn the optimal HVAC control policy (supporting continuous actions) for maintaining thermal comfort. Furthermore, a framework that merges the model-free and model-based approaches is presented in [27]. The authors aim to achieve optimal HEMS control of smart building subsystems by implementing Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to approximate real-world HVAC operations, eventually targeting to build realistic DRL training environments. Finally, the authors in [28] merge the DRL framework with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks that provide future state information for the solar radiation intensity, the electricity price and the outside temperature, aiming to enhance HVAC control stability.

Finally, the problem of the smart home energy management system described in this work shares similar objectives with the charging of Electric Vehicles (EVs) and the energy management for hybrid EVs optimization problems. In specific, the EV charging scheduling, as well as the development of energy and emission management strategies problems can be considered as Markov Decision Processes (MDP) and DRL algorithms that target to optimize the total charging time, the origin-destination distance, the fuel consumption and the emissions have been developed to address them [29]–[32]. In addition, a similar approach to the present work that has been developed for the EV charging control problem is presented in [33]. The algorithm is based on DDPG that aims to provide an intelligent control strategy for satisfying the user's battery energy demands and minimizing the charging cost, while also taking into consideration the output of LSTM networks. Evidently, similar DRL-based methods as the approach presented herein are utilized to provide intelligent energy management frameworks, since they can cope with dynamic environments that depend on multiple inter-correlated parameters and, in general with non-convex optimization problems [34]. However, the smart home energy management problem exhibits additional challenges due to the multiple environmental parameters that affect the decisions of the intelligent agent. In this context, it is practically intractable to estimate the impact of the dynamic ambient temperature, the solar radiation, the humidity and the household demands on the control of the indoor environment.

B. Contributions

The previous subsection indicates that various research studies have tackled the HEMS modeling and decision making problem from different perspectives, either taking into consideration a suitable thermal model of the smart home environment or by formulating a data-driven approach based on the observability and the actions of a DRL algorithm. Following the latter concept, we propose a hybrid DDPG/LSTM algorithm that combines the model-free DRL framework of an agent that learns the optimal policy for continuous HVAC and ESS control and the predictive capabilities of LSTM networks for future energy consumption requests and energy generated by renewable sources. The innovation points of the present work can be summarized as follows:

- The present work is based on a realistic mathematical modeling, considering several aspects of a modern smart

home environment [35]. In particular, the model takes into account the energy generated by renewable sources, the energy demands of the household, an ESS that is used as a storage energy unit, the market-dependent electricity price, as well as the inside and ambient temperature. Our approach targets to minimize the energy cost that is required for the non-controllable energy consumption requests and the operation of the controllable HVAC system, by promoting the self-sufficient satisfaction of the smart home energy demands based on the energy gathered by renewable sources.

- The LSTM models that are incorporated in our method enable the forecasting of the smart homes' energy consumption requests and the energy generated by renewable sources in future time instances, based on historical data. The prediction considers the time-varying parameters of the smart home, e.g. solar panel-produced energy over time. It should be noted that the LSTM models are trained based on the dataset of an individual smart home, being tailored to the specific area (for instance ambient temperature or solar energy generation is strongly correlated to the household location) and to the energy habits of the residents (e.g., energy demands are increased in cases that the inhabitant is working remotely).
- The designed DRL algorithm that is based on DDPG actor-critic model, aims to optimize the energy provided to the HVAC system and the charging/discharging of the ESS. The DDPG model observes the dynamic state of the problem (time-varying modeling parameters of the smart home and the environment), including the output of the LSTMs (i.e., the predicted energy generation from renewable sources and the requested energy for load activation) that describe future states of the environment. It is also notable that the inclusion of LSTM predictions in the DRL state enables self-recovery when there are missing real-time energy data (missing energy values can be replaced by the latest available LSTM predictions to ensure uninterrupted DRL inference). The optimization objective of the DDPG model is to maintain a comfortable temperature range inside the home, while at the same time minimizing the energy cost.
- Our method is extendable to multiple smart homes that can exchange the individual energy surplus gathered by renewable sources in order to get a zero-sum energy footprint, utilizing the framework of federated learning [36]. To this end, the proposed approach promotes the use of renewable energy inside a smart home and also inside an energy community consisting of multiple homes, covering their specific energy needs via locally produced renewable energy, while also minimizing the grid utilization and the associated cost (energy that is drawn from the grid is minimal).
- Extensive simulation results using real-world data indicate that our method exhibits a beneficial trade-off between the energy cost and the temperature comfort in the household, resulting in negligible temperature deviations compared to rule-based energy regulation techniques, while achieving at least 5% energy cost reduction

Fig. 1. Modeling of the Smart Home, including the information flow from the environment to the Smart Meter and the Grid.

compared to the non LSTM-assisted DDPG method.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, the modeling of the smart home environment is presented, along with the formulation of the energy cost minimization problem. Evidently, we assume that an energy node exists in a smart home environment, generating energy from some renewable energy source, while also having an ESS to store the excess energy. Furthermore, the Smart Home has an internal temperature and also exhibits its individual energy consumption requests, representing the energy demands of its residents.

A. Smart-Home modeling

The Smart Home environment and the related parameters that are considered in this work are depicted in Fig. 1. First, the smart home includes a renewable energy source like photovoltaics (PV) or micro wind turbine generators (mWTGs) that is used to gather power. In addition, it is assumed that the environment includes an ESS that can be used to store power, and can be utilized to reduce the net-energy demand from the grid by providing locally stored energy. Furthermore, we assume that there are several types of loads inside the household, representing true energy demands: (i) non-shiftable loads that need to be satisfied immediately (e.g., television, lights, charging laptop, etc.). When non-shiftable demands originate from the smart home environment, the request must be covered without any time delay; (ii) shiftable and non-interruptible loads (for instance, a dishwasher or a washing machine). The request for these loads can be scheduled beforehand, but cannot be interrupted while in operation; (iii) controllable loads (for example the HVAC system, heat pumps, etc.). As aforementioned, this type of load represents a significant percentage of the household energy demands, and can be controlled over a discrete time duration. Finally, a sensor provides measurements about the temperature inside the household, while temperature indications from the ambient environment outside the home can be also gathered.

In this context, all these data originating from the smart home environment are acknowledged to the smart meter,

which is the entity that registers the production and consumption requests and connects the household to the utility power grid. In case that the energy consumption requests (immediate, scheduled or controllable) cannot be fulfilled locally by the generated energy from renewable sources or the excess energy stored in the ESS, the shortage is provided directly from the utility grid. This option is usually the most cost inefficient, since the required energy deficit to cover the household demands follows the fluctuations of the market. It is worth noting that all the parameters involved in the modeling are time varying. However, we discretize the time t into slots, $t \in [1, S]$, where S is the total number of time slots and we assume that the mean value of the involved parameters reflects the smart home environment during each individual time slot (e.g., the internal temperature during each time slot is stable). To this end, the system parameters can be monitored in low or high granularity if required by adjusting the duration of each time slot, ranging for instance from sub-minute time scales up to several hours.

The energy that is stored in the ESS at time t is denoted as E_t , while its temporal evolution can be described by [35]:

$$E_{t+1} = E_t + \omega_\phi \phi_t + \frac{\theta_t}{\omega_\theta}, \quad (1)$$

where $0 < \omega_\phi \leq 1$ and $0 < \omega_\theta \leq 1$ are the coefficients for the charging and discharging operations of the storage system, while ϕ_t and θ_t represent the charging (from the utility grid) and discharging (towards the loads of the smart home) energy during the time slot t respectively. In addition, the energy level of the ESS at any given time t is bounded between a minimum and a maximum energy capacity amount (typically expressed in Ah or Wh):

$$E^{min} \leq E_t \leq E^{max}. \quad (2)$$

Similar constraints can be formulated for the charging and discharging rates. We follow the formalism of defining a positive-valued ϕ_t variable for the charging rate and a negative-valued θ_t variable for the discharge rate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \phi_t \leq \phi^{max} \\ -\theta^{max} \leq \theta_t \leq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ^{max} and θ^{max} are expressed in Watts and no simultaneous ESS charging and discharging operations during a time slot can occur:

$$\phi_t \cdot \theta_t = 0. \quad (4)$$

In this work, the optimization target is to maintain a comfortable temperature inside the home, while minimizing the energy cost of the controllable HVAC operation. Towards this direction, the continuous energy p_t that is provided to the HVAC system in each time slot is bounded by the following constraint:

$$0 \leq p_t \leq p^{max}, \quad (5)$$

where p^{max} is the peak power in Watts consumed by the HVAC system during one time slot. It is worth noting that herein we use interchangeably the terms energy and power,

considering that the energy (measured in Wh) describes the amount of power consumption or production over the time slot t . Furthermore, the dynamics of the indoor temperature can be described by the following equation [37]–[39]:

$$T_{t+1}^{in} = \epsilon T_t^{in} + (1 - \epsilon) \left(T_t^{out} - p_t \frac{\eta}{A} \right), \quad (6)$$

where T_t^{out} is the outside ambient temperature, ϵ is the inertia factor that balances between the inside and the outside temperatures, η is the thermal conversion efficiency (heating) or the coefficient of performance (cooling), and A is the overall thermal conductivity in kW/°C. Evidently, the indoor temperature evolution depends on three terms: (i) the previous indoor temperature; (ii) the outdoor environmental temperature during time slot t ; (iii) a term based on the controllable power provided to the HVAC system, taking into account the building dynamics. It should be noted that although (6) describes a specific indoor temperature dynamic model, more complex models (e.g., taking into account the indoor relative humidity) can be adapted in the proposed methodology to include different dimensions of the thermal comfort [26], [40], [41].

In order to maintain a comfortable environment inside the smart home, we assume that the indoor temperature T_t^{in} must be bounded within a certain temperature range:

$$T^{min} \leq T_t^{in} \leq T^{max}. \quad (7)$$

Additionally, the power that is gathered by the renewable energy sources is denoted by q_t and can be immediately utilized to cover the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands of the smart home during the time slot t , denoted as ℓ_t . A power balance equation can be formulated to balance the overall power consumption and generation dynamics, taking into account the power drawn from the grid, the produced local power from renewable sources and the power that is requested by the smart home residents. The aggregated power supply should be equal to the served power demand:

$$q_t + g_t - \theta_t = \phi_t + p_t + \ell_t, \quad (8)$$

where g_t is the power exchange between the smart meter and the grid in kW required to balance the power deficit or surplus. Therefore, $g_t \leq 0$ reflects an energy surplus of the system that can be sold back to the grid with a market-dependent selling electricity price μ_t . On the contrary, $g_t > 0$ indicates that the smart home has an energy deficit and therefore, will purchase energy from the grid to cover its energy demands with a time varying buying electricity price ν_t . The selling and buying electricity prices are typically linearly related with a scaling factor χ , i.e., $\mu_t = \chi \nu_t$. In the present work, we utilize the grid as an infinite power source that can cover the power demands of the individual household (energy deficit) and we do not consider the scenario of energy surplus that can be sold back to the grid. In this way, we promote the local production of energy from renewable sources that is consumed locally. It should be noted that this approach can be implemented to an energy community that consist of multiple smart homes; in this case, the energy surplus of an individual household can

be provided to cover the energy demands of a neighbouring house, minimizing the energy footprint of the community.

B. Energy Cost Minimization Problem

The minimization of the energy cost that is related to the operation of the controllable HVAC system involves, on the one hand, the actual electricity price ν_t of the power that is drawn from the grid, and, on the other hand, the implicit depreciation cost of the ESS. Regarding the latter term, the frequent discharging or charging may significantly decrease the lifetime of the ESS. By defining a depreciation coefficient ρ , we can formulate the optimization problem as follows:

$$(P_1) : \min_{p_t, \theta_t, \phi_t} \sum_{t=1}^S \mathbb{E} \{ \max\{\nu_t g_t, 0\} + \rho(\phi_t + |\theta_t|) \} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad (1) - (8).$$

The expectation operator \mathbb{E} is calculated for the considered time slots S over the randomness of all the related parameters that are described in (1) - (8), e.g., the ambient temperature T_t^{out} , the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands of the household ℓ_t , the fluctuating market value of electricity ν_t , etc. Furthermore, in order to find a solution to (P_1) , the power provided to the HVAC system p_t , as well as the charge/discharge power of the ESS (ϕ_t or θ_t) need to be defined in each time slot t , also taking into account the impact of these control variables on the environment, as well as ensure the non-violation of the involved constraints.

In principle, (P_1) is a very challenging problem, since: (i) the dynamics of the thermal environment of a building are extremely complex and cannot be accurately described; (ii) the power balance equation includes several random system parameters (power gathered from renewable sources, energy demands, etc.) that cannot be estimated or controlled to a sufficient extent; (iii) the first term of the energy cost involves the market-dependent electricity prices that cannot be predicted; (iv) the decision variables for the energy cost minimization problem (p_t , ϕ_t , θ_t) are not independent; (v) current actions may have an impact on future decisions of the system. Regarding the latter point, in terms of energy cost it may be beneficial for instance to fully charge the ESS on a day of cheaper electricity market value and store the energy for a future day with increased household energy demands (and possibly reduced sunlight).

Problem (P_1) can be formulated as a decision-making MDP problem, since the indoor temperature at the next time instance T_{t+1}^{in} calculated by (6) depends on the indoor temperature at time t , the HVAC power input, the ambient temperature T_t^{out} and the building characteristics. Moreover, the energy level of the ESS in the next time slot E_{t+1} computed by (1) depends on the current stored energy in the ESS and the discharging/charging power. Evidently, the indoor temperature dynamics controlled by HVAC power and the ESS dynamics depend only on the state of the time slot t and the performed control actions and are independent of previous states and actions.

In this context, the control actions on the smart home environment (HVAC input power and ESS charging/discharging) can be considered as MDPs and the optimization problem can be solved by reinforcement learning algorithms [35]. It should be noted that not all the parameters of the environment state are Markovian, i.e., the renewable power generation q_t , the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands ℓ_t and the buying electricity price ν_t may exhibit long-range temporal correlations, or even inter-dependencies with other variables. For instance, high electricity prices may influence the energy consumption profile of the household residents. However, approximating the overall optimization problem as an MDP and solving it via reinforcement learning methods is still a valid approach [42], [43]. Complementing the reinforcement learning method for solving the optimization problem, this work also includes LSTM networks to enhance the performance of the algorithm for the non-Markovian environment parameters, i.e., for forecasting the renewable power generation and the non-shiftable and non-interruptible household energy demands.

C. Forecasting Models

This section presents the time-series forecasting functionality that is embedded in the modeling process of the smart home energy management system (see also Fig. 1). To estimate future solar generation and household energy demands, there are mainly two approaches that are widely-used in the literature: the first is the hypothesis-driven, in which a specific mathematical model of the solar generation dynamics is assumed, and the second is the AI-driven, in which massive historical data are used to train and infer an ML model. The effectiveness of the latter highly depends on the size of the historical dataset that is used (vast amount of data usually leads to enhanced predictive abilities of the ML model), as well as the on the proactiveness ability (i.e. models provide better predictions for short-term predictions than for long-term ones). The most significant advantage of using AI-driven forecasting techniques is that there is no need to make any assumption about the solar power or the energy demands dynamics; instead, the only requirement is to collect massive samples -ideally, real samples- during many years from many locations and, then, use them to analyse and train a neural network. For instance, the intrinsic characteristics of the solar generation patterns, such as the seasonality, periodicity, systematic anomalies, are inherently recorded in historical datasets, allowing the neural model to fit and learn these dynamics. Noteworthy, all of the available approaches provide just estimations of the upcoming solar power values, each one presenting a certain prediction error score depending the available data, the assumptions made, and the model training configuration.

In this work, the time-series forecasting functionality is provided by the LSTM models that are trained on a real-world historical datasets, originating from residential households from the area of central Europe. In this context, the ML models target to enable the prediction of two smart home's parameters that are involved in the energy cost minimization problem, i.e., the power that is gathered by the renewable sources q_t and the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands

Fig. 2. Time series of the energy gathered by renewable sources (the historical dataset is depicted in black color). The input data that are fed to the LSTM model are shown in blue for a sample period of 1 day, while the label of the LSTM network is shown in red at the time slot of 60 hours.

ℓ_t . The forecasting of these parameters in the future time slot (or in the upcoming few time slots) $t + M$, where $M > 1$, is based on historical data, considering the temporal evolution of these time series. These parameters are typically periodical or at least exhibit seasonality. For instance, the average solar panel generated power is expected to be lower during the winter for the northern hemisphere and the energy demands are usually minimal after midnight. A sample real dataset from a smart home for the hourly energy gathered by solar panels is depicted in Fig. 2 for a period of 1 week in January.

The real dataset of the energy gathered by solar panels can be transformed in an input/output format in order to train the LSTM model for time-series forecasting. To this end, part of the temporal evolution of the locally-generated energy is used as input in the LSTM model (time window of past values depicted) and the energy gathered by the solar panels in the upcoming time slot is used as a label in the regression problem. It should be noted that the temporal evolution of the gathered energy exhibits daily periodicity. Using open household data for power generation¹, we construct the dataset in a labeled form (input/output format), the values of power are scaled in the range of $[0, 1]$ by using a MinMaxScaler². The scaling of the power values is performed only in the training dataset in order to avoid information leakage to the testing set. The scaled training data are therefore utilized to train the LSTM model, while the inverse scaler is applied during the LSTM inference phase.

The parameter of the time window of past values is formally denoted as N and the input in the LSTM network is formally described as $\hat{q} = [\hat{q}_{t-N}, \hat{q}_{t-N+1}, \dots, \hat{q}_t]$, while the label is the \hat{q}_{t+M} and the \hat{q} represents the scaled values of the energy gathered by renewable sources. Fig. 3 shows the LSTM network architecture for the prediction of the locally produced energy. Four stacked hidden layers were used to assemble

¹https://data.open-power-system-data.org/household_data/

²<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.preprocessing.MinMaxScaler.html>

Fig. 3. Properties of the LSTM neural network, including the feature vector $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ (time window of past values) for predicting the target sample \hat{q}_{t+M} . The LSTM network consists of four stacked hidden layers, each one having 50 LSTM units with 20% dropout rate.

the LSTM network, each of them consisting of 50 LSTM units. Moreover, a dropout rate of 20% is utilized to avoid overfitting of the LSTM network in the training dataset and the loss function (difference between the actual and the predicted values of the produced energy from renewable sources \hat{q}_{t+M}) during the training process backpropagation was the Mean Squared Error (MSE).

It is worth mentioning that an identical LSTM network as the one depicted in Fig. 3 was also designed for the forecasting of the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands ℓ_t in terms of dimensionality, loss function and dropout rate. Without loss of generality, the same length of the past values time window N was utilized, leading to scaled LSTM input of similar dimensionality, i.e., $\hat{\ell} = [\hat{\ell}_{t-N}, \hat{\ell}_{t-N+1}, \dots, \hat{\ell}_t]$, while the scaled label can be expressed as $\hat{\ell}_{t+M}$. Results related to the fine-tuning of the LSTM hyperparameters for both networks are shown in ‘‘Simulation Results’’ section. Following the training of both models, the weights of the LSTM network for renewable energy forecasting are denoted as w^q , while the weights of the LSTM network for energy demands forecasting are denoted as w^ℓ . Noteworthy, the LSTM models can be adapted to also incorporate local weather data as additional input feature vectors. For instance, a feature vector $\hat{\mathbf{z}} = [\hat{z}_{t-N}, \hat{z}_{t-N+1}, \dots, \hat{z}_t]$, or even weather forecast data $\hat{\mathbf{z}} = [\hat{z}_{t-N}, \hat{z}_{t-N+1}, \dots, \hat{z}_t, \hat{z}_{t+1}]$, reflecting local weather data (such as the precipitation, humidity and wind) could be also used for prediction of future energy production or energy demands.

D. Automated Home Energy Management Agent

This section focuses on the description of the automated DRL-based energy management agent that is incorporated in the smart home environment of Fig. 1. As aforementioned, the intelligent agent aims to optimize the input power provided to the HVAC system, as well as the charging/discharging of the ESS. These processes can be modeled as MDP, since the

Fig. 4. Interaction between the DRL agent and the smart home environment, illustrating the state, action and reward functionalities.

involved parameters of the future state in principle depend only on their values of the current state, and not on previous states and actions. Although this statement is not completely valid for all the involved components of the environment, such as the energy gathered by renewable sources and the outdoor temperature which can exhibit long-range correlations, it has been verified that reinforcement learning algorithms that are based on trial-and-error learning process can still empirically solve problems similar to (P_1) [35], [38], [42].

Therefore, we can conceptualize the environment of a Smart Home as a MDP, considering our DRL intelligent agent to be the HEMS. The interaction of the DRL agent with the smart home environment is depicted in Fig. 4. The agent operates in discrete time slots $t \in [1, S]$, deciding (recommending actions that are applied on the system) on whether to provide input power to the HVAC system or provide/draw power from the ESS for charging/discharging purposes. This decision is made based on the rest of the variables that are observed by the smart home, i.e., ESS level, power demands, outdoor temperature, etc. The state of the environment is thus observed at each time point and the DRL agent is the responsible entity for providing an action that is beneficial for the environment, according to the optimization objectives set during the reinforcement learning process (reward function). The state, action and reward of the DRL agent are described below.

1) *State of the Smart Home Environment:* The state of the environment consists of all the time-varying parameters of the smart home that are relevant to the energy management problem under investigation, such as the temperature inside the smart home, the ambient outdoor temperature, the power gathered by the solar panels or other renewable energy sources, the ESS level, etc. According to the smart home modeling, the environment state, denoted s_t , consists of the following information:

- Renewable power generation q_t .
- Renewable power generation for future time instances q_{t+M} predicted by the appropriate LSTM model.
- Non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands ℓ_t .
- Non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands for future time instances ℓ_{t+M} predicted by the suitable LSTM model.
- ESS energy level E_t .
- Outdoor ambient temperature T_t^{out} .

- Indoor temperature T_t^{in} .
- Buying electricity price ν_t .
- time slot index in a day t' ($t' = \text{mod}(t, 24)$).

The state of the smart home environment that is acknowledged at each time slot to the DRL agent is therefore described by the following tuple:

$$s_t = (q_t, q_{t+M}, \ell_t, \ell_{t+M}, E_t, T_t^{out}, T_t^{in}, \nu_t, t') \quad (10)$$

2) *Action of the Intelligent DRL Agent:* The action of the HEMS agent is two-fold: (i) manipulating the input power p_t of the HVAC system for indoor temperature control in order to satisfy the users comfort; (ii) deciding whether the ESS system will be charged or discharged during this time slot with rates ϕ_t or θ_t respectively, in order to store or utilize previously stored ESS energy to minimize the overall energy consumption of the smart home. Since no simultaneous ESS charging and discharging can occur, we can model the latter HEMS decision using a single variable κ_t , that takes values inside the range:

$$\kappa_t : [-\theta^{max}, \phi^{max}]. \quad (11)$$

To this end, when the value of κ_t is positive, the ESS system is charged:

$$\kappa_t > 0 \Rightarrow \kappa_t = \phi_t, \quad (12)$$

whereas when the value of κ_t is negative, the ESS system is discharged:

$$\kappa_t < 0 \Rightarrow \kappa_t = \theta_t. \quad (13)$$

It should be noted that the two action variables can be scaled, since scaled values are typically beneficial for the training process of the neural networks [44]. The input power to the HVAC system is scaled based on (5) in the range of $[0, 1]$, denoted as \hat{p}_t , whereas the ESS charging/discharging power is scaled in the range of $[-1, 1]$ based on (3), denoted as $\hat{\kappa}_t$, and without loss of generality, $\theta^{max} = \phi^{max}$ is assumed. Using the scaled variable values, the action tuple of the DRL agent can be expressed as $\alpha_t = (\hat{p}_t, \hat{\kappa}_t)$.

3) *Reward Function:* As illustrated in Fig. 4, after observing the current state s_t and suggesting the action α_t , the DRL agent receives a reward r_{t+1} , quantifying whether the selected action was beneficial towards the optimization objectives of the energy management problem. In this context, the target of the DRL HEMS agent is to regulate the provided power to the HVAC system and the ESS charging/ discharging power in each time slot in order to maintain the temperature comfort inside the smart home, as well as minimize the cost related to the ESS usage and the energy cost provided by the grid. The ML model also promotes the general objectives of the building energy management problem, since we target to inherently maximize the use of locally produced renewable energy inside a smart home, covering its specific energy needs, while also minimizing the grid utilization and the associated cost.

Reflecting on the above optimization objectives, the reward function of the HEMS agent consist of three terms:

(i) The deviation from the indoors thermal comfort range, as expressed by (7). The DRL agent aims to maintain the user's comfort and receives a penalty (negative reward) when the indoor temperature is out of bounds. The indoor temperature refers to the new state of the smart home environment, which is calculated based on (6) and involves the action of the DRL agent. The penalty is proportional to the temperature deviation and can be expressed by:

$$r_{1,t+1}(s_{t+1}, \alpha_t) = ([T_t^{in} - T^{max}]^+ + [T^{min} - T_t^{in}]^-), \quad (14)$$

specifying that $r_{1,t+1} = 0$ if $T^{min} \leq T_t^{in} \leq T^{max}$, whereas $r_{1,t+1} = T_t^{in} - T^{max}$ for $T_t^{in} > T^{max}$ and $r_{1,t+1} = T^{min} - T_t^{in}$ for $T_t^{in} < T^{min}$.

(ii) The cost of the energy provided to the HVAC system based on the buying ν_t electricity price g_t from the utility grid. It should be noted that the amount of power that will be drawn from the utility grid g_t (as aforementioned, we do not consider the scenario of energy surplus that can be sold back to the grid) is calculated by solving the power balance equation (8), following the decision of the DRL agent ($\hat{p}_t, \hat{\kappa}_t$). The penalty of the DRL agent related to the energy cost is by:

$$r_{2,t+1}(s_t, \alpha_t) = \max\{\nu_t g_t, 0\} \quad (15)$$

(iii) The cost related to the depreciation of the ESS due to often charging or discharging is given as a negative reward to the DRL agent (the units of the depreciation coefficient ρ is \$/kW):

$$r_{3,t+1}(s_t, \alpha_t) = \rho(\phi_t + |\theta_t|) \quad (16)$$

The overall combined negative reward can be expressed by:

$$r_{t+1} = -r_{1,t+1} - \beta(r_{2,t+1} + r_{3,t+1}), \quad (17)$$

where β is a trade-off coefficient, balancing between the temperature comfort inside the household and the energy cost. It is worth mentioning that a variant of the proposed approach can include additional measures of thermal comfort or any complex indoor temperature dynamics model. Concerning the indoor relative humidity, for instance, its temporal variation could be included in the system state of the smart home environment and also in the action tuple, i.e., the humidity configured by the HVAC system and the reward function. Finally, an equation representing the temporal evolution of the indoor humidity, taking into account most of the factors affecting the moisture in a room can be employed to enable the prediction of humidity change during HVAC operation [41].

III. DEEP DETERMINISTIC POLICY GRADIENT DESIGN AND ALGORITHMIC PROCESS

In this section, we describe the design of the DDPG model that controls the smart home environment, utilizing the forecasting capabilities of the LSTMs, i.e., leveraging the prediction of the upcoming power gathered by the solar panels and the forecast of the energy requests. In principle, the DDPG-based energy management algorithm can tackle problems that require continuous state and action spaces and belongs to the category of actor/critic component interaction to update the policy and value function [45]. Since several variables of the environment state are in general continuous

(e.g., temperature, energy demands, etc.) and the action tuple also includes continuous variables, the selection of DDPG-based scheme avoids the explosion of the state and action spaces.

The DDPG scheme consists of an actor neural network, that takes as input the state space s_t and delivers the recommended action α_t , and a critic neural network, that takes as input the state space s_t and the action α_t suggested by the actor, while its output is the quantified evaluation of the action selected by the actor network for this state through an action-value function, i.e., $Q(s_t, \alpha_t)$. Using memory experience replay and target networks mechanisms, the critic network updates its weights before computing $Q(s_t, \alpha_t)$ [46]. Next, the policy gradient can be computed and used to update the weight of the actor network. Following this trial-and-error training process, the target actor and critic networks are softly update to ensure a stable algorithm learning procedure until convergence. The algorithm for the training of the DDPG agent is described in Algorithm 1.

The algorithmic process starts by randomly initializing the replay memory \mathcal{F} that contains transition tuples $(f(s_t), \alpha_t, r_{t+1}, f(s_{t+1}))$, where $f(s_t)$ is the the pre-process function applied to variables of the environment state (as aforementioned, the pre-process function can be a MinMaxScaler to scale the state variables in the range of $[0, 1]$). Then, the critic network $Q(f(s_t), \alpha_t|w^Q)$ and the actor network $\lambda(f(s_t)|w^\lambda)$ are also randomly initialized with weights that are denoted as w^Q and w^λ respectively. Moreover, the duplicate target critic and target actor networks are also initialized, by transferring the weights from the original critic and actor networks, i.e., $w^{Q'} \leftarrow w^Q$ and $w^{\lambda'} \leftarrow w^\lambda$.

The main loop of the algorithm runs for H training episodes, initializing several parameters of the environment state s_0 . In specific, the ESS energy level E_t and the indoor temperature T_t^{in} are randomly initialized, while a random day from the available dataset is also selected, to be utilized as a starting time instance point for the current episode (we assume that the simulation starts at the beginning of the day, i.e., time slot $t' = 0$). For the selected starting point, the values of all the required parameters are obtained from the time-series datasets. In specific, the renewable power generation time series $\mathbf{q} = [q_t, q_{t-1}, \dots, q_{t-N}]$ and the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands $\ell = [\ell_t, \ell_{t-1}, \dots, \ell_{t-N}]$ required for the LSTM model inference are provided by the available datasets, as well as the outdoor ambient temperature T_t^{out} and the buying electricity price ν_t .

Then, the algorithm proceeds in within-episode time slots, reflecting on the time-varying conditions of the environment. The pre-process function is applied to the time window values of the renewable power generation $f(\mathbf{q})$ and the non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands $f(\ell)$ in order to obtain the normalized values $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = [\hat{q}_{t-N}, \hat{q}_{t-N+1}, \dots, \hat{q}_t]$ and $\hat{\ell} = [\hat{\ell}_{t-N}, \hat{\ell}_{t-N+1}, \dots, \hat{\ell}_t]$ and infer the two LSTM models with weights w^q and w^ℓ to calculate the respective predicted values \hat{q}_{t+M} and $\hat{\ell}_{t+M}$. Moreover, the rest of the variables comprising the state $(q_t, \ell_t, E_t, T_t^{out}, T_t^{in}, \nu_t, t')$ are also pre-processed in order to assemble the environment state $f(s_t)$. The algorithmic process continues by selecting an action α_t , which can be

Algorithm 1 HEMS agent training with DDPG

Input: Renewable power generation time series, non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands time series, outdoor ambient temperature time series, buying electricity price time series, weights of LSTM network for renewable power forecasting w^q , weights of LSTM network for energy demands forecasting w^ℓ .

Output: The weights of actor network w^λ and critic network w^Q of the DDPG model.

- 1: Random initialization of replay memory \mathcal{F} of size L and preprocess function $f(s_t)$.
 - 2: Random initialization of the critic network $Q(f(s_t), \alpha_t|w^Q)$ and actor network $\lambda(f(s_t)|w^\lambda)$ with weights w^Q and w^λ .
 - 3: Initialize target critic and actor networks by copying the weights from the original networks, i.e., $w^{Q'} \leftarrow w^Q$ and $w^{\lambda'} \leftarrow w^\lambda$.
 - 4: **for** $episode = 1, 2, \dots, H$ **do**
 - 5: Random initialization of environment state parameters, including E_t, T_t^{in} and random selection of time instance.
 - 6: Initialization of $T_t^{out}, \nu_t, [q_t, q_{t-1}, \dots, q_{t-N}]$ and $[\ell_t, \ell_{t-1}, \dots, \ell_{t-N}]$.
 - 7: **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, S$ **do**
 - 8: Pre-process $f(\mathbf{q})$ to get $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and infer the LSTM model with weights w^q to calculate \hat{q}_{t+M} .
 - 9: Pre-process $f(\ell)$ to get $\hat{\ell}$ and infer the LSTM model with weights w^ℓ to calculate $\hat{\ell}_{t+M}$.
 - 10: Pre-process $q_t, \ell_t, E_t, T_t^{out}, T_t^{in}, \nu_t, t'$ in order to assemble the pre-processed state $f(s_t)$.
 - 11: Select action α_t according to (18) (exploration/exploitation).
 - 12: Implement selected action α_t on the smart home environment using equations (1), (6), (8) and (17), receive next state s_{t+1} and reward r_{t+1} .
 - 13: Store the transition tuple $(f(s_t), \alpha_t, r_{t+1}, f(s_{t+1}))$ in \mathcal{F} .
 - 14: Sample a random mini-batch of B transition tuples from the replay memory \mathcal{F} , i.e., $(f(s_j), \alpha_j, r_{j+1}, f(s_{j+1}))$, $1 \leq j \leq B$.
 - 15: Calculate the expected state action values:
 $y_j = \gamma Q'(f(s_{j+1}), \lambda'(f(s_{j+1})|w^{\lambda'})|w^{Q'}) + r_{j+1}$
 - 16: Update critic network by minimizing the smooth L_1 loss, using (20).
 - 17: Update actor policy using sampled policy gradient:
 $\frac{1}{B} \sum_{j=1}^B \nabla_{\alpha} Q(f(s), \alpha|w^Q)|_{s_j, \alpha_j} \nabla_{w^\lambda} \lambda(f(s)|w^\lambda)|_{s_j}$
 - 18: Update target critic and actor networks:
 - 19: $w^{Q'} \leftarrow \tau w^Q + (1 - \tau) w^{Q'}$
 - 20: $w^{\lambda'} \leftarrow \tau w^\lambda + (1 - \tau) w^{\lambda'}$
 - 21: **end for**
 - 22: **end for**
-

mathematically defined as:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \lambda(f(s_t)|w^\lambda), & \text{if } \zeta_t > \sigma_{ep} \\ (\mathcal{O}_1, \mathcal{O}_2), & \text{if } \zeta_t \leq \sigma_{ep} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

representing the exploration/exploitation trade-off selected by the DDPG agent. In (18), the variable ζ_t is a random number in the range of (0, 1) used to select between exploration (random action) and exploitation (action provided by the actor network), while the \mathcal{O}_1 variable is a random number in the range of [0, 1] for the input power to the HVAC system \hat{p}_t action and \mathcal{O}_2 is a random number in the range of [-1, 1] for the ESS charging/discharging \hat{k}_t action. Furthermore, without loss of generality, the transition between exploration and exploitation of the agent is selected to be linearly decaying between episodes, i.e., $\sigma_{ep} = \sigma_{ep-1} - 2/H$ and $\sigma_0 = 1$, denoting that the agent will perform only exploitative actions in the second half of the training episodes H .

The algorithm continues by implementing the selected action α_t on the smart home environment, i.e., calculating the dynamic values of the variables using equations (1), (6) and (8). Therefore the agent observes the next state of the environment s_{t+1} and receives the reward r_{t+1} according to (17). It should be noted that the next state of the environment s_{t+1} involves the time-series dataset variables T_{t+1}^{out} , ν_{t+1} , $[q_{t+1}, q_t, \dots, q_{t+1-N}]$ and $[\ell_{t+1}, \ell_t, \dots, \ell_{t+1-N}]$, as well as the inference process of both LSTM models to calculate \hat{q}_{t+1+M} and $\hat{\ell}_{t+1+M}$. Once the next state is obtained, it is normalized and the transition tuple $(f(s_t), \alpha_t, r_{t+1}, f(s_{t+1}))$ is stored in the replay memory \mathcal{F} .

In order to update the weights of the critic network and the actor policy, a random mini-batch of B transition tuples $(f(s_i), \alpha_i, r_{i+1}, f(s_{i+1}))$, $1 \leq i \leq B$ is sampled from the replay memory \mathcal{F} . For this mini-batch, the expected state action values are calculated based on the Bellman equation [45], [47]:

$$y_j = \gamma Q'(f(s_{j+1}), \lambda'(f(s_{j+1})|w^{\lambda'})|w^{Q'}) + r_{j+1}, \quad (19)$$

where the target critic and actor networks with weights $w^{Q'}$ and $w^{\lambda'}$ are utilized to estimate the so-called long-time reward (expected state action values) and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ is the discount factor. The weights of the critic network are then updated by minimizing the smooth L_1 loss:

$$L_1 = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{j=1}^B \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}^2/2b, & \text{if } |\mathcal{L}| < b \\ |\mathcal{L}| - b/2, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

and $\mathcal{L} = (y_j - Q(f(s_j), \alpha_j|w^Q))$. Then, the sampled policy gradient can be also calculated by [46]:

$$\nabla_{w^\lambda} J \approx \frac{1}{B} \sum_{j=1}^B \nabla_{\alpha} Q(f(s), \alpha|w^Q)|_{s_j, \alpha_j} \nabla_{w^\lambda} \lambda(f(s)|w^\lambda)|_{s_j}, \quad (21)$$

which is used to update the actor policy. Following the algorithmic procedure of the DDPG agent training, the weights of the duplicate target critic and actor networks are updated by using $w^{Q'} \leftarrow \tau w^Q + (1-\tau)w^{Q'}$ and $w^{\lambda'} \leftarrow \tau w^\lambda + (1-\tau)w^{\lambda'}$, while the update variable τ can be selected for a conservative policy iteration rule (soft update), i.e., $\tau \ll 1$. The architectures of the actor and critic (as well as the target actor and critic) networks in the proposed DDPG-based energy management

Fig. 5. Architecture and dimensionality of the actor and critic networks of the DDPG agent for the energy management system.

algorithm are illustrated in Fig. 5, where two hidden layers are included in the actor network, while the critic network takes as input the state space s_t , the action α_t suggested by the actor and combines them, consisting overall of four hidden layers.

IV. RESULTS

In the following subsections, we present the results of the LSTM forecasting models, as well as the results of the intelligent DDPG agent for the smart home energy management system.

A. LSTM-based Forecasting Results

Similar process was conducted for the training of the two LSTM networks, i.e., the network for forecasting the energy production from solar panels and the power consumption of the smart home. Initially, an 90/10 split of the dataset was performed for the training/testing data for both networks. As aforementioned, the LSTM networks consist of four stacked hidden layers, each of them with 50 units, with a dropout rate of 20% to avoid overfitting and MSE is selected as the loss function (see Fig. 3). Moreover, the values of the input/output labeled dataset were scaled in the range of [0, 1]. Then, the hyper-parameters of the training process were fine-tuned, including the learning rate L_R and the time window of past values N . It is worth mentioning that the future time slot for the prediction is selected to be $M = 1$, since the granularity of the time slot is 1 hour and the HEMS agent's actions can be considered sufficiently proactive within this time limit [17], [19], [35]. The resulting LSTM training losses are shown in Fig. 6 (a) and (c) for both LSTM networks in the course of 20 epochs.

The training losses converge to 6 Wh and 9 Wh for the energy generation and for the energy consumption LSTM networks respectively. The optimal values for the training of both LSTM networks are $L_R = 0.01$ and $N = 24$, since higher length of time window of past values $N = 168$ results in similar MSE errors. The smallest value of N , however, is in principle optimal for purposes of lowest computation complexity and higher inference latency. By employing the optimal values for the training of the LSTM networks, the accuracy on the testing (validation) dataset can be obtained. The resulting predicted values are compared to the actual values from the dataset in Fig. 6(b) and (d) for the two networks in the time course of 1 week (168 hours). The fine-tuned LSTM model for the energy generation forecast from solar panels achieves a mean absolute error (MAE) of approximately 40 Wh, following the daily time-domain periodicity, as well as accurately predicting the peak values of energy generation, as demonstrated in Fig. 6(b). Finally, it is worth mentioning that a sensitivity analysis of the trained LSTM model can be conducted to reveal the importance of the time lag selection by individually varying the input model features for different levels [48]. Although the sensitivity analysis reveals the critical importance of the most recent value that is used for model inference, i.e., \hat{q}_t in the case of energy generation forecast, it is assumed that the input values to the LSTM model are known with significant accuracy, since they are directly measured from the household equipment (solar panels or smart meter) and exhibit negligible variability.

Furthermore, the fine-tuned LSTM model for the energy consumption prediction of the household achieves a MAE of approximately 200 Wh compared to the actual values of energy demands. As shown in Fig. 6(d), the LSTM model follows the daily time-domain trends of the energy demands, identifying the busy hours of the household in terms of energy requests. Nevertheless, the forecasting in this case is significantly more challenging, since the energy requests of a household are in general irregular, resulting in arbitrary peak values of energy consumption that cannot be accurately predicted.

B. DDPG-assisted Automated Energy Management System

In this subsection, we initially present the results related to the training and stabilization of the DDPG network and associated parameters. Moreover, we illustrate the dependence of the reward function on the optimization trade-off parameter β . Then, we utilized the proposed scheme with its fine-tuned parameters to compare its performance with baselines, including a reactive rule-based HEMS control method, a DQN-assisted approach and a DDPG intelligent agent without the use of LSTMs.

1) *Training Results:* As aforementioned, the simulation results are based on an open household dataset for renewable energy generation from solar panels and non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy consumption, as well as the environmental data for the outdoors temperature from the region of Germany in Europe. Moreover, the time varying market

Fig. 6. Results related to the training of the LSTM networks: (a) MSE training loss of the energy generation model in the course of 20 epochs; (b) actual versus LSTM-predicted values of the energy generation for 1 week of the testing dataset; (c) MSE training loss of the energy consumption model in the course of 20 epochs; (d) actual versus LSTM-predicted values of the energy consumption for 1 week of the testing dataset.

prices for the electricity are also obtained online³. Finally, it is assumed that the weights for the two LSTM networks w^g and w^ℓ , required as input for the execution of the proposed algorithm, have already been obtained, as described in the previous subsection.

Apart from the time-series real measurements (renewable energy and household energy demands originating from residential households), the parameters related to the smart home environment that were used in the simulations herein required from the HEMS agent training algorithm are tabulated in Table I. It should be noted that these parameters either originate from the literature (e.g., the parameters for the thermal building dynamics η and A according to [35], [37], [38]), or can be adjusted according to the smart home equipment (e.g., ESS capacity) and the optimization targets. In specific, we configure the temperature comfort utility between $T^{min} = 19.5$ °C and $T^{max} = 22.5$ °C, the maximum power of the HVAC system to 10 kW and we use different values of the thermal conversion efficiency (heating) or the coefficient of performance (cooling) parameter η , i.e., $\eta = 2.5$ for cooling and $\eta = -1$ for heating in order to comply with both functionalities of the HVAC system. Finally, the ESS minimum and maximum capacities (0.6 and 10 kWh respectively) are important system parameters, since they impact the energy that can be drawn or provided from/to the grid when the electricity price is low/high. Please note that although the selection of the above variables aims to realistically represent the smart home dynamics, different environment parameters (e.g. different experimentation with HVAC power values, different ESS technologies) can be directly configured to the proposed approach, enabling the simulation of more complex scenarios⁴.

Furthermore, the parameters of the training algorithm re-

³<https://data.nordpoolgroup.com/auction/day-ahead/prices?deliveryDate=latest¤cy=EUR&aggregation=Hourly&deliveryAreas=AT>

⁴<https://github.com/sospanti/Energy-Management-System>

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS RELATED TO THE SMART HOME
ENVIRONMENT AND THE DDPG TRAINING ALGORITHM

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
E^{min} (kWh)	0.6	H	1000
E^{max} (kWh)	10	N	24
$\omega_\phi, \omega_\theta$	0.95	M	1
ϕ^{max}, θ^{max} (kW)	3	L_R	0.01
ϵ	0.7	$L_{R_{ac}}$	10^{-4}
p^{max} (kW)	10	$L_{R_{cr}}$	10^{-5}
η	+2.5/-1	N_{ac}	(300, 600)
A (kW/°F)	0.14	N_{cr}	(300, 600, 600, 600)
T^{min} (°C)	19.5	B	32
T^{max} (°C)	22.5	b	1
χ	0.9	L	120000
ρ (€/kWh)	1	τ	10^{-3}
		γ	0.99

lated to the DDPG learning process are also tabulated in Table I. The L_R , M and N are the learning rate, future time slot and window of past values parameters of the LSTM networks fine-tuned in the previous section. The $L_{R_{ac}}$ and $L_{R_{cr}}$ are the learning rates of the actor and critic networks respectively, while N_{ac} and N_{cr} represent the dimensionalities of the two networks. Two hidden layers were utilized in the actor network and four hidden layers in the critic network, as also depicted in Fig. 5. Notably, the learning parameters were fine-tuned after extensive simulations, including the discount factor γ of the Bellman equation (19) and the soft update parameter for the duplicate target critic and actor networks τ .

During the training process, the trade-off parameter β was varied to investigate its impact on the learning process. The resulting reward functions are shown in Fig. 7(a) for $H = 1000$ training episodes and for two different inter-episode number of steps, i.e., $S = 24$ (the agent interacts with the environment for one continuous day during each episode) and $S = 168$ (the agent interacts with the environment for one continuous week during each episode). In these steps within each episode, the agent tries to find the best policy towards the time-varying smart home environment, taking into account the temperature, the ESS, the renewable energy, the pricing and the building dynamics. The environment is again randomly initialized in the next episode and the intelligent HEMS agent starts again the trial and error learning process. It should be remarked that a linear decay policy was selected for the transition between the exploration and exploitation phases of the DDPG agent.

Fig. 7. (a) Learning curves for different values of the trade-off optimization parameter β , showcasing the convergence of the DDPG training process. (b) Average energy cost and temperature deviation with respect to increasing values of the parameter β , specifying the trade-off between temperature comfort and energy cost.

As observed from Fig. 7, the reward functions for $\beta = 0$ demonstrate convergence to zero, exhibiting low fluctuations with variability during the exploration/exploitation phase for both values of the inter-episode number S . In this case, the agent aims to maintain the indoor temperature regardless of the energy cost. Thus, the DDPG model stabilizes the time-domain temperature regardless of ambient temperature, solar panel produced energy and household energy demands, providing the required input power to the HVAC system to maintain the temperature within the comfort bounds. On the contrary, the reward functions converge in increasingly lower values with respect to incremental values of β , denoting the trade-off optimization between the energy cost and the temperature comfort. For visualization purposes, the learning curves (reward functions) for the different trade-off parameters β are scaled in Fig. 7 according to the following expression:

$$r_t = -\log_{10}(1 - r_t), \quad (22)$$

since the values of the reward function are negative ($r_t < 0$) by definition in (17). To this end, different DDPG models for varying trade-off parameter β are trained and can be used for HEMS control, where only the trained actor network is used for inference purposes. Moreover, based on the results, the inter-episode number of steps is selected to be $S = 24$, since this accelerates the model training in dynamic environmental conditions, as well as making the process more lightweight and computation-effective.

The performance of the DDPG models is evaluated against the specific optimization objectives for varying trade-off coefficient β in Fig. 7(b), depicting the average energy cost (including the cost of the HVAC input power and the ESS depreciation cost) and the average temperature deviation for the duration of 1 day. As observed from the results, the average value of the energy cost decreases with increasing β , whereas the the mean temperature deviation from the comfort bounds increases. To this end, the trained DDPG actors provide minimum temperature deviation of approximately 0.2 °C for $\beta = 0$, while resulting in a temperature deviation of 0.36 °C for $\beta = 2$ with approximately 80% less energy cost, indicating that the intelligent HEMS agent achieves a satisfactory trade-off between temperature comfort and energy cost. In this context, the DDPG model draws more energy from the grid and/or frequently charges and discharges the ESS system when required to fulfill the consumption demands, whereas in case that the energy cost is important (increasing β), the agent tries to maximize the use of renewable energy and minimize the interaction of the smart home with the utility grid.

2) *Baseline Comparison:* In this subsection, we present the results of our proposed algorithm in two diverse scenarios in terms of environmental parameters: (i) the first scenario presents the performance of the HEMS agent during summer months, with relatively high outdoor temperatures and sunlight duration; (ii) the second scenario considers the HEMS operation and performance during winter, with low outdoor temperatures and sunlight duration, as well as inflated household energy consumption demands. The performance

Fig. 8. Comparison between the proposed hybrid DDPG/LSTM algorithm and the baseline results for the first (summer) scenario, with $\beta = 1.8$: (a) Energy provided to the HVAC system and solar energy generated by the solar panels; (b) Indoor temperature based on the HEMS control of the different schemes and variations of the outdoor temperature. The temperature comfort bounds are also depicted; (c) Energy exchange between the ESS and the utility grid.

results of our DDPG-based method with LSTM assistance are compared to the following baselines in both scenarios:

Baseline 1: Rule-based HVAC control. This reactive scheme is designed only for indoor temperature comfort, without considering the use of the ESS [49]. Specifically, the HVAC system in the next time slot will be turned on if the indoor temperature is out of bounds, based on the constraints of (7). The energy provided to the HVAC system can be expressed as:

$$\alpha_{t+1}^{react} = \begin{cases} p_{t+1}^{react}, & \text{if } T_t^{in} > T^{max} \text{ or } T_t^{in} < T^{min} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

where the p_{t+1}^{react} can be found based on (6):

$$p_{t+1}^{react} = \frac{A}{\eta} \left(T_t^{out} - \left[\frac{T^{max} + T^{min}}{2} - \frac{\epsilon T_t^{in}}{1 - \epsilon} \right] \right). \quad (24)$$

This rule-based reactive scheme virtually aims to emulate the end-user behavior (household resident) by adjusting the HVAC power after the indoor temperature (or most specifically the "feel-like" temperature) is outside the designated comfort limits.

Baseline 2: DDPG without the LSTM forecasting scheme. This algorithm intends to minimize the energy cost of the HEMS agent, without utilizing the forecasting capabilities of the proposed approach. In this context, the same equations that formulate the smart home environment and the optimization problem are still valid. Nevertheless, the state space observed by the DRL agent in this case is seven-fold, i.e., does not include the forecasting values of the renewable energy generation q_{t+M} and non-shiftable and non-interruptible energy demands ℓ_{t+M} that are predicted by the LSTM models in (10). The purpose of this baseline is to assess the functionality of the forecasting LSTM networks in the overall DDPG performance.

Baseline 3: DQN-based scheme. This algorithm is implemented directly on the smart home environment, using the mathematical model and the involved parameters presented in this work. To this end, the DQN model is trained based on the state space and reward function of Baseline 2 for HVAC and ESS power control, providing discrete output values for the action variables instead of continuous values suggested by the DDPG algorithms. Without loss of generality, the DQN network and target network includes in total 100 output layers corresponding to discrete actions, i.e., 10 discrete levels for the power provided to the HVAC system and 10 levels for the ESS charging/discharging power. Regarding the parameters of the DQN networks, we have utilized the same dimensions for the hidden layers as in the case of the DDPG agent, as reported in Table I, while the fine-tuned learning rate is $L_{RDQN} = 10^{-4}$. Based on the performance comparison between the results of the proposed algorithm and the DQN method, the impact of the continuous action space offered by the DDPG on the energy cost can be quantified.

The results are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 for the summer and the winter scenarios respectively. As observed in Fig. 8(a), the energy provided to the HVAC system by the DDPG-based methods is significantly lower than the DQN approach, indicating that the former methods utilize more effectively the energy gathered by renewable sources. In specific, the average hourly energy provided to the HVAC by employing the proposed approach is approximately 50 Wh compared to 90 Wh suggested by the DDPG without LSTM scheme, while 49 Wh are on average allocated by the rule-based method and 100 Wh by the DQN-based scheme. Furthermore, Fig. 8(b) shows the temporal variations of the indoor and outdoor temperatures for the different algorithms, denoting that the average temperature deviation of the proposed hybrid scheme is 0.37 °C, as compared to 0.38, 0.6 and 0.4 °C for the DDPG without LSTM, DQN and rule-based methods. Finally, the temporal variations of the ESS level are shown in Fig. 8(c) for

Fig. 9. Comparison between the proposed hybrid DDPG/LSTM algorithm and the baselines for the second (winter) scenario, with $\beta = 1.8$: (a) Energy provided to the HVAC system and solar energy generated by the solar panels; (b) Indoor temperature based on the HEMS control of the different schemes and variations of the outdoor temperature. The temperature comfort bounds are also depicted; (c) Energy exchange between the ESS and the utility grid.

the three ML-assisted approaches, where it is observed that the temporal variations of the ESS follow the same pattern, albeit more fine-grained for the two DDPG-based methods due to the discrete nature of the DQN algorithm. Using these results, the required energy drawn from the grid to balance the deficit after the actions of the intelligent agents can be calculated for the three ML-assisted methods, providing estimations about the cost.

Regarding the second (winter) scenario, the time-varying energy provided to the HVAC system is depicted in Fig. 9(a), where the average hourly energy suggested by the proposed hybrid scheme is approximately 5.4 kWh, as compared to the average energy of 5.6, 5.3 and 4.6 kWh allocated by the DDPG

without LSTM, DQN and rule-based methods respectively. Moreover, the variations of the indoor temperature shown in Fig. 9(b) result in average temperature deviations of 0, 0, 0.03 and 2.4 °C for the actions suggested by the proposed scheme, the DDPG without LSTM approach, the DQN and the rule-based methods, while the temporal variations of the ESS energy level are illustrated in Fig. 9(c). In this scenario, it is observed that the renewable energy gathered by the solar panels is significantly lower as compared to the summer scenario due to reduced sunlight. In addition, the outdoor temperature is considerably lower than the targeted temperature bounds, leading to increased energy consumption and cost.

Evidently, the proposed hybrid scheme exhibits a reduced energy cost of more than 12% with respect to the DDPG without LSTM and the DQN solutions and similar energy cost with the rule-based method in the summer scenario, whereas also exhibiting slightly lower deviation of the indoor temperature in the summer scenario with respect to all three baseline algorithms. Moreover, a decreased cost of the proposed approach of approximately 5% in the winter scenario with respect to the DDPG without LSTM solution and the DQN method is observed, whereas the temperature deviation is effectively zero for the three methods. It is worth mentioning that although the rule-based method provides the most economical solution in the winter scenario, the average temperature deviation is considerably increased (> 2 °C). On the other hand, the hybrid DDPG/LSTM algorithm exhibits a satisfactory trade-off between the energy cost and the temperature comfort in the household in both winter and summer scenarios, resulting in marginal temperature deviation of less than 1 °C.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a hybrid DDPG/LSTM algorithm for HEMS control (HVAC and ESS system) of a smart home environment, combining the decision-making features of the DRL framework and the predictive capabilities of the LSTM networks for the household energy consumption requests and the generated renewable energy. For this purpose, we first establish a realistic mathematical modeling of the smart home environment, taking into account multiple parameters. The objective of our algorithm is to minimize the energy cost of a smart home, while maintaining its indoor temperature comfort and covering its energy requests, inherently promoting the use of renewable energy and reducing its energy signature. The hybrid DDPG/LSTM method is tested using real-world data, while the extensive simulation results and the comparison with baseline methods illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach in achieving an optimal trade-off between the temperature deviation and the energy cost. As our future work, we aim to extend our method to include additional input features for energy generation forecasting, as well as incorporate different thermal comfort variables. Moreover, we target to extend this approach in multiple smart home environments that can exchange the individual power surplus gathered by renewable sources in order to achieve a zero-sum energy footprint of an energy community.

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